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Maximising Strategic Agility for Corporate Advantage: A Theoretical Reflection

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed maximizing strategic agility for corporate advantage: A theoretical reflection. The study was predicated on the Resource-Based View (RBV) theory. It was conceptualized using strategic agility (responsiveness, sensitivity and adaptive capacity) to predict corporate advantage measures of cost advantage, differentiation and innovativeness. The literature review served as a basis to balance reasoning and reach a logical conclusion on the subject matter. The study highlighted various scholars' views on the meaning and definitions of strategic agility and corporate advantage. The study also reviewed the empirical findings of other studies with respect to the relationship and significance of strategic agility on corporate advantage. Evidence from the scholars' empirical findings depicts the existence of a connection between strategic agility and corporate advantage. Based on the theoretical and empirical reviews, this study concluded that maximizing strategic agility is fundamental for improving corporate advantage. This conclusion implies that organizations through maximizing strategic agility can achieve corporate advantage and overall business performance.

Keywords: Strategic Agility, Corporate Advantage, Responsiveness, Sensitivity, Adaptive Capacity.

INTRODUCTION

Today's business landscape is dynamic and ever-changing all over the world. These changes are triggered by factors such as technological advancements, globalization, competition, economic, political, social and environmental challenges (Anjas, 2022). The negative impact of these fluxes is that organizations are subjected to conditions of uncertainties as they experience changes in customers tastes and preferences (Arbussa *et al.*, 2017). To overcome these challenges, organizations must constantly adapt and evolve to stay competitive. According to Arokodare and Asikhia (2020), an organization's ability to quickly and effectively respond to changes within its environment is crucial to success. Responding to changes, often referred to as "strategic agility," has become pivotal in achieving corporate advantage (Battistella *et al.*, 2017). Strategic agility is the capability of an organization to swiftly and effectively respond to changes in its external environment while aligning internal resources to exploit emerging opportunities and mitigate risks (Doz, 2020). It involves the ability to think and act flexibly, make rapid decisions, and execute strategies in a dynamic and uncertain world. Strategic agility is a new terminology, and one of the key approaches for handling changes and facing up to dangers so that to direct organizations towards building an internal vision that enables them to obtain capabilities necessary for competition as well as an external vision that helps them seize up opportunities brought about by changes (Nkuda, 2017). According to Oyedijo (2012), strategic agility helps an organization with the ability to focus on strategic

aspects of predicting external variables in the business environment, demonstrating rapid interaction with conditions and markets, and building a targeted strategy for rapid response.

Business organizations all over the world are competitive. Companies need to adapt to changing market conditions, including shifts in demand, pricing pressures, and emerging competitors. Strategic agility can help in identifying and responding to these challenges. Strategic agility implies the ability of a company to quickly adapt and respond to externalities in its environment while maintaining a clear and focused long-term strategic direction (Ogunnusi *et al.*, 2020). The imperative of this concept to organizations is evidenced in the fact that the industry is subject to various dynamic factors that can significantly impact their operations and corporate advantage. Unarguably, economic and regulatory environment is volatile in almost every country of the world (Omopariola *et al.*, 2022). Changes in government policies, regulations, or economic conditions can affect business performance. Organizations that can quickly adapt to these changes and realign their strategies will have a competitive advantage. Strategic agility is essential for organizations to seize opportunities as new projects emerge and to adjust their strategies to meet the specific requirements of each project. Strategic agility can give organizations the ability to adapt strategies to suit the dynamic and challenging business environment in their industries (Akinshipe *et al.*, 2019). Companies that can quickly respond to changes in regulations, technology, competition, and market conditions while staying true to their long-term strategic goals will be better positioned to gain a corporate advantage regardless of the industry.

Corporate management studies (Teece, 2018) have established that developing agile strategies are expected to strategically position corporate organizations on the apex ladder regardless of any industry. Notwithstanding the significance of strategic agility and its impact on corporate advantage, many organizations have continued to suffer disappointments resulting from changes that occur within the business environment and which in most cases make them suffer losses in their operations (Suhair & Muthana, 2022). To overcome these challenges, corporations should be able to develop strategic agility in line with their business goals and criteria. Teece (2018) explained the importance of adopting strategic agility in meeting organizations' goals. According to Oyedijo (2012), strategic agility helps organizations to mitigate the impact of changes that have the ability to cause disruptions within an organization. However, it appears that organizations in Nigeria are bereft of the significance and role of strategic agility in the achievement of corporate advantage. Existing literature shows that there is paucity of documented studies that depict the theoretical and empirical relationship between these concepts in the context of organizations in Nigeria. Besides, the documented studies have reported conflicting results; while some studies (such as Nkuda, 2017; Oyedijo, 2012) revealed presence of between the concepts, others (such as Suhair & Muthana, 2022) decline any interaction between the variables. Motivated by this dearth of theoretical and empirical studies and a couple of empirical inconsistencies, this paper theoretically explores the significance of maximizing strategic agility and how it contributes to corporate advantage.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Fig. 1.1: Conceptual framework of the relationship between strategic agility and corporate advantage.

Source: Authors' illustration

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION OF THE STUDY: RESOURCE-BASED VIEW.

The Resource-Based View (RBV) is a theoretical framework in strategic management that emphasizes the importance of a firm's internal resources and capabilities as key determinants of its corporate advantage. The RBV is associated with Jay Barney (Barney, 1991). Barney is a lucid exponent in the field of strategic management who has made significant contributions to the RBV. His work emphasizes the role of valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources in achieving sustainable corporate advantage. The RBV assumes that firms differ in their resource endowments, and these differences in resource assets are a primary source of corporate advantage. This postulation highlights the idea that firms have unique combinations of resources that set them apart from competitors. Resources are often immobile or difficult to transfer between firms. This immobility is a key factor in resource-based advantage (Tidd & Bessant, 2018). Resources that can be easily acquired by competitors are less likely to provide a sustainable corporate advantage. Resources must add value to the firm and enable it to exploit opportunities or defend against threats in the external environment. Not all resources are equally valuable, and a resource is valuable only if it contributes to the firm's performance. To be a source of corporate advantage, a resource must be rare among the firm's current and potential competitors. If everyone has access to the same resource, it is unlikely to lead to an advantage. Resources should be difficult to imitate or replicate. Imitability implies that competitors cannot easily copy or reproduce the resource, ensuring that the advantage is sustained (Pycraft *et al.*, 2018). The RBV recognizes the dynamic nature of resources and capabilities. Firms must continuously adapt and evolve their resources and capabilities to maintain a corporate advantage in a changing environment. The RBV acknowledges that a firm's ability to combine and leverage its resources effectively is a source of advantage (Hopp & Spearman, 2019). The significance of the RBV to the present study is that emphasizing the importance of valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources is key to corporate advantage position. The resource-based view provides a foundation for understanding how firms can achieve and sustain a corporate

advantage by focusing on their internal resources and capabilities. By recognizing the importance of strategic agility as a veritable resource, organizations can develop strategies that are better aligned with their competitive strengths.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept Of Strategic Agility

The strategic agility phenomenon not only refers to change, but it also emphasizes the idea of rapid and fruitful change. This statement is in tandem with the official definition of agility as "the ability to move quickly and easily (Hitt *et al.*, 2017). Strategic agility is the capacity of an organization to quickly and effectively adapt its strategies, structures, processes, and resources to navigate and capitalize on emerging opportunities and challenges in a rapidly changing and uncertain business environment (Teece, 2018). It involves the ability to think and act flexibly, make rapid decisions, and implement strategies that are responsive to dynamic market conditions. Agility represents the organization's ability to constantly adapt to an environment that is changing and uncertain, where corporate advantage is often temporary and strategic moves are frequently required. In fact, strategic agility becomes especially important in a work environment that is highly competitive (Oyedijo, 2012). Strategic agility, in addressing growing strategic imbalances and disruptions, requires the creation of new business models and categories rather than rearranging old products and categories (Kale *et al.*, 2019). Strategic agility reflects the extent to which an organization is sensitive to changes that occur within the business environment, its ability to adapting to these changes through creativity as well as its ability to foresee unexpected surprises both inside and outside its working environment, proactively responding to them in an effective and rapid manner so that threats or challenges are transformed into opportunities (Helfat & Peteraf, 2015) through the process of reorganization, swift responsiveness while having the capability to make reforms (Haider & Kayani, 2020). It also means the development and implementation of other actions and measures that control market risks and uncertainties (Kale *et al.*, 2019).

Responsiveness: Responsiveness refers to an organization's ability to adapt, react, and adjust its strategies, plans, and actions quickly and effectively in response to changing external conditions and emerging opportunities or threats. It reflects the organization's capacity to remain agile and proactive in the face of uncertainty and dynamic market forces. In business management, strategic responsiveness is the capacity to sense changes in the market, customer preferences, and competitive landscapes, and to adjust the firm's strategies accordingly in a timely manner (Simsek *et al.*, 2015; Chatzoglou & Chatzoudes, 2020)

Sensitivity: Sensitivity, in various contexts, refers to the capacity to detect or respond to changes, variations, or stimuli, often in a precise and accurate manner. The term can be applied in a wide range of fields, from scientific research to economics and healthcare. In economics, sensitivity analysis refers to the examination of how changes in input variables impact the output or outcomes in economic models, such as financial forecasts and investment decisions (Ben-Haim, 2016).

Adaptive Capacity: Adaptive capacity relates to the capacity of systems, institutions, humans and other organisms to adjust to potential damage, to take advantage of opportunities, or to respond to consequences. In organizational management, adaptive capacity signifies an organization's ability to adjust its strategies, structures, and processes to effectively respond to changing market conditions, technology advancements, and competitive pressures (Teece, 2018).

CORPORATE ADVANTAGE

Corporate advantage refers to the unique qualities, resources, or strategies that enable a business to outperform its competitors in a given market or industry, leading to superior performance, increased market share, and sustained profitability. It is the distinct edge a company has over its competitors, often stemming from its unique capabilities, cost structure, differentiated products, or innovative approaches (Porter, 2008). In marketing, corporate advantage represents a company's ability to create and promote a unique value proposition that sets it apart from rivals and attracts customers (Kotler & Armstrong, 2021). According to Christensen *et al.* (2015), corporate advantage is achieved through developing and

leveraging unique intellectual property, patents, and proprietary technologies. This study adopts cost advantage, differentiation and innovativeness as measures of corporate advantage.

Cost Advantage: Cost advantage, often referred to as cost leadership, is a strategic advantage that a company achieves by producing goods or providing services at a lower cost than its competitors while maintaining a similar level of quality. This cost advantage allows the company to offer competitive prices or higher profitability (Pycraft *et al.*, 2018). Cost advantage is a strategic position that enables a company to deliver products or services at a lower cost than competitors, allowing it to either offer lower prices or achieve higher profit margins (Hopp & Spearman, 2019).

Differentiation: Differentiation, in the context of business and marketing strategy, refers to the process of making a company's products, services, or brand unique in ways that are valued by customers. This uniqueness can take the form of distinct features, design, quality, or other factors that set the company apart from its competitors (Zeithaml *et al.*, 2018).

Innovativeness: Innovativeness refers to an organization's or individual's ability to generate new and creative ideas, concepts, products, services, or processes and the willingness to implement these innovations. It involves a proactive approach to change and a commitment to continuous improvement. In the context of business strategy, innovativeness is the capacity of an organization to create and implement new and unique products, services, or processes that provide a corporate advantage and drive growth (Tidd & Bessant, 2018).

MAXIMIZING STRATEGIC AGILITY FOR CORPORATE ADVANTAGE

Strategic agility has significant impact on corporate advantage of organizations. One very remarkable element of the Nigerian business environment is its rapidly changing status, in terms of consumer preferences, market conditions, and competitive landscapes. An SBU that is agile enough to respond quickly to these changes can gain a corporate advantage over its competitors. Teece (2018) avers that strategic agility enables businesses to quickly respond to changes in the market, such as shifts in consumer preferences, regulatory changes, or economic fluctuations. This ability to adapt can help organizations stay competitive and even capitalize on emerging opportunities. According to Oyedijo (2012), because strategic agility often involves a culture of innovation and continuous improvement, organizations that are quick to innovate and introduce new products or services can gain a competitive edge, especially in industries where innovation is highly valued. Nkuda (2017) remarked that in a country like Nigeria, where political, economic, and social risks can be significant, strategic agility allows organizations to proactively manage and mitigate risks. This might involve diversifying operations, entering new markets, or adjusting business strategies to minimize potential disruptions. Agile organizations are often better at understanding and meeting the evolving needs of their customers. By staying attuned to customer feedback and preferences, they can create a loyal customer base, which can be a sustainable source of corporate advantage. When businesses can quickly respond to competitor actions or market developments, they can pre-empt potential threats and capitalize on the weaknesses of competitors.

Nigeria's regulatory environment is fickle and very external to the business organization, companies that can adapt to new regulations or policy changes can maintain compliance while minimizing disruptions to their operations. Strategic agility offers the possibility to rearrange business processes in the face of unpredictable environmental changes (Battistella *et al.*, 2017) and prevents stagnation (Arbussa *et al.*, 2017). Nkuda (2017) divulged that strategic agility has theoretical impact on corporate advantage. Arokodare and Asikhia (2020) theoretically investigated the link between strategic agility and firm performance through strategic foresight as part of antecedent of strategic foresight. The Dynamic Capability and Entrepreneurship Innovation theories were the underpinning theories for the study. Thus, a conceptual model was developed to depict the interaction between strategic agility and firm performance through strategic foresight. Majority of past literature shown that strategic agility and strategic foresight have significantly enhanced firm superior performance.

The impact of strategic agility is also documented in empirical literature. For instance, Suhair and Muthana (2022) examined strategic agility and its impact on strategic recovery of hospitals in Iraq. The

research was applied to a purposeful sample of 95 administrative leaders in the researched hospitals, while using SPSS for data processing with the help of statistical means of “percentage, arithmetic median, standard deviation, coefficient of correlation, and coefficient of regression. The study revealed that strategic agility has a significant impact on strategic recovery. Arokodare *et al.* (2020) examined strategic agility and corporate advantage of oil and gas marketing companies: The moderating effect of information technology capability and strategic foresight in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study employed survey research design. The study population was 515 managers of major oil and gas marketing companies. Total enumeration was used and a structured questionnaire was adapted and validated. The instrument was reliable and valid: Cronbach’s alpha coefficients ranged from 0.734 to 0.814, and KMO values were greater than 0.5. 515 copies of questionnaires were distributed and 480 returned useable, giving a response rate of 93.2%. Hierarchical regression method was used for data analysis. Findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between strategic agility and corporate advantage in oil and gas marketing companies. Anjas (2022) attempted to determine the influence of strategic agility on marketing sustainability achievements in Iraqi private hospitals. The study was applied to private Iraqi hospitals located in Baghdad. In order to achieve the objectives of the study. The researcher designed a questionnaire consisting of (20) paragraph to collect the preliminary information from the sample of the study. SPSS was used to analyze and evaluate the hypothesis. The results of the study showed that there was an important effect of some of the strategic agility dimensions on the competitiveness of operations in Iraqi private hospitals.

CONCLUSION

This study carefully reviewed the theoretical significance of maximizing strategic agility for corporate advantage. The study highlighted various scholars’ views on the meaning and definitions of strategic agility using responsiveness, sensitivity and adaptive capacity as the key indicators, as well as corporate advantage in terms of cost advantage, differentiation and innovativeness. The study also reviewed the empirical findings of other studies with regard to the relationship and significance of strategic agility on corporate advantage. Evidence from the theoretical and empirical findings depicts the existence of connection between strategic agility and corporate advantage. Based on the theoretical and empirical reviews, this study concludes that maximizing strategic agility is a fundament for improving corporate advantage.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the outcome of this paper, the authors recommend as follows:

1. Organisations should adopt strategies to enable them sense changes in the market, customer preferences and competitive landscape to achieve corporate advantage and overall business performance.
2. Businesses should be able to detect or respond to changes in a precise and accurate manner to achieve corporate advantage and overall business performance.
3. Organisations should adopt strategies, structure and processes to effectively respond to changing market conditions, technological advancement and competitive pressures to achieve corporate advantage and overall business performance.

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